

Identification of linear data-driven models for large-scale power systems

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Abstract—The linearization of the full model of electrical power systems is of great significance for the adoption of linear analysis techniques to examine the system’s dynamic characteristics, as well as for the design and tuning of practical controllers. Typically, the state-space model of the power system is first obtained from the time domain model. Linear analysis and controller tuning are then performed utilizing the linear state-space model. This approach however often has several practical limitations, such as the unavailability of a time domain model, when only simulation or measurement data is available, or the lack of linearization capability in the software tool in which the time domain model is available. Moreover, the linearization of the time domain models of large-scale power systems results in very high-dimension state-space models, which greatly complicates further analysis. To this aim, in this paper, suitable linear data-driven models of reduced order are identified for power systems to retain the most relevant modes of oscillations of the original system. A commercial rigorous software is used for the data generation and a well-established Python toolbox is used for the model identification: different models and techniques are applied and then compared in terms of accuracy and simplicity.

Index Terms—Process modeling, power systems, modal identification, system identification

I. INTRODUCTION

Interconnections in power systems increase significantly their reliability, since, in the case of failure of any generating station, the grid can share promptly the corresponding missing load [1]. The analysis of such large interconnected power systems requires detailed non-linear models including different generation and transmission devices and their controllers. Building such large and complex models in any rigorous simulation tool is often a very challenging and time-consuming effort. In addition to the non-linear time domain models, obtaining equivalent linear models of the power systems is of great importance for understanding the dynamic characteristics

of the whole system and the dynamic interactions between the different components.

In the power system context, stability can be considered as the capability to stay in equilibrium under normal operating conditions or when subjected to external perturbations. If the perturbation is little, it is known as small-signal stability [2]. As well-known, linearization around a static equilibrium point is possible in the case of small perturbations which cause only little deviations. Thus, electrical systems can be well represented by linear dynamic models [3]. Small-signal analysis of power systems, as well as the tuning procedures for grid controllers such as the Power System Stabilizers (PSS) and the Power Oscillation Damping (POD), imply a linear representation at certain operating modes and conditions, that is, require a linear model built around a steady-state operating point of the nonlinear one [4]. This requires either maintaining and regularly updating a linear model of the entire power system, which involves a huge amount of effort and time, or linearizing the time domain model using certain analytical or numerical routines, which only few simulation software are capable of performing. Therefore, the software-free linearization of the whole power system model becomes a key aspect for the design and tuning of practical grid controllers [5]–[7]. Modal identification techniques are indeed essential to compute equivalent linear models of power systems directly from time-domain simulations run in rigorous software [8].

The objective of this work is thus to derive a set of practical linear data-driven models for different types of power systems that guarantees a good compromise between the accuracy of representation and the simplicity of use. The identified models, with a reduced order, aim to describe the most significant features of the dynamic response of the original system, that is, the most relevant modes of oscillation, to be then used for the proper tuning of system controllers. The remainder of the paper is briefly reported. Section II describes the various models and methods adopted, while Section III illustrates

three significant case studies analyzed for the scope. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section IV.

II. MODELS AND METHODS

Some details about the models and the methods employed to analyze the considered power systems are here given.

A. Simulation software

The data were firstly generated with *PowerFactory*, a well-established rigorous simulation software for power grids developed by DIGSILENT [9]. The software was used remotely in Python by means of the corresponding library *powerfactory*, for the simulation run and data collection.

The whole system identification procedure was then performed with SIPPY - Systems Identification Package for PYthon [10], previously developed by two of the authors of this paper. This user-friendly tool is fully open-source and available as a repository on GitHub [11].

B. Input signal design

Traditional step tests were chosen for the model identification. It is well known that a good input signal has to be *informative*, that is, it has to excite the system in a wide range of frequencies, in order to collect information on its various modes of oscillation. Common examples of informative signals are GBN (Generalized Binary Noise) and PRBS (Pseudo-Random Binary Signal) [12]. Nevertheless, these signals are not feasible in the context of power grids for two main reasons. Firstly, persistent inputs may act as excessive disturbances to guarantee a safe working regime since recommended input signals are limited variations with respect to the normal operating condition. Secondly, most equipment, like synchronous generators, are expensive devices subject to heavy wear and tear, so it is not appropriate to induce further stress with complex input signals. Therefore, step response tests were adopted, as they proved to be small perturbations that are still able to induce low-frequency oscillatory modes of different types, such as local and inter-area modes, as well as control and torsional modes [3].

C. Linear models

Two different linear formulations have been used in the present analysis: input-output and state-space models [13].

As known, state-space models can be well identified by subspace methods in one of their typical structures, that is process, innovation, or predictor form. Subspace methods are classified into two main categories: *traditional* and *parsimonious*. The three most used traditional methods (N4SID [14], MOESP [15], CVA [16]), which can be grouped into a unifying theorem [17], mainly differ by the weighting matrices used in the Singular Value Decomposition (SVD), which represents the core of the procedures. On the other hand, parsimonious methods remove non-causal terms in the linear projection by enforcing block-triangular matrices, typically using innovation or predictor form. The major difference lies in the algorithm which obtains causal models and can be sequential (PARSIM-S [18]), parallel (PARSIM-P [19]), or mixed (PARSIM-K

[20]). This last method has an appealing feature: it assumes that the input signal is correlated with the output noise and hence is consistent with data collected in a closed-loop mode.

In particular, in this work, four different sub-space methods are used (N4SID, MOESP, CVA, and PARSIM-K) and the five different approaches available in [11] for the selection of the best model order are investigated. This means that fixed-order models, models with an order selected based on a threshold set on the singular values, and three well-established information criteria (Akaike, corrected Akaike, and Bayesian) are tested.

As a comparison, input-output models are also considered: ARX (AutoRegressive with eXogenous inputs) and ARMAX (AutoRegressive-Moving-Average with eXogenous inputs) models, in particular. In the case of multivariable systems, a series of multiple input - single output (MISO) subsystems are considered.

The quality of the identified models is evaluated by the Normalized Mean Squared Errors (NMSE) between the original output y and the model output \hat{y} , defined as follows:

$$NMSE = \frac{1}{\sigma_y N} \sum_{k=0}^N (y_k - \hat{y}_k)^2 \quad (1)$$

where σ_y is the standard deviation of the original output, and N is the number of samples.

III. CASE STUDIES

The results for three selected power systems of increasing size and complexity are presented in this section.

A. The synchronous generator

As a first example, a single synchronous power generator is analyzed. This machine converts mechanical power into electrical power with an alternate current at a desired voltage and frequency, and is connected to an infinite busbar. Figure 1 shows the simplified block diagram of the considered device with its three main components:

- **Excitation system:** which produces the generator field voltage V_f by processing and amplifying the input control signal.
- **Generator:** which generates the electrical power P from the mechanical power of the turbine and the field voltage from the excitation system.
- **Power System Stabilizer - PSS:** which provides an additional input signal to damp oscillations of the power system; its main scope is indeed to reduce the generator rotor oscillations by controlling its excitation.

The various signals shown in Figure 1 include the reference voltage V_{ref} , the stabilizing voltage V_s , the field excitation voltage V_f , and the terminal voltage V_t , all in V or p.u., the active power P [MW], and the rotor speed ω_r [p.u.], where p.u. means *per unit*. As an example, the rotor speed is expressed as a fraction of its electrical unit, that is, the nominal speed, which, for the considered generator, is 3000 rpm.

The three-block generator is described within *PowerFactory* with a rigorous nonlinear time domain model and also by a linearized model of high-order, comprised of 40 states which

Fig. 1. Simplified block diagram of the single synchronous generator.

Fig. 2. Time responses for the single generator: original nonlinear system and fixed-order linear models.

results impractical for controller tuning purposes. This high-order model is also because the excitation system model includes additional limiter models, such as the UEL (Under Excitation Limiter), the OEL (Over Excitation Limiter), SCL (Stator Current Limiter), and Volts/Hertz limiter. The major objective of the present analysis is thus to derive linear models of low-order that can identify the dominant modes of the original system. Details of the various analyses are illustrated.

1) *Fixed-order models*: In this first scenario, the four considered subspace methods were used to identify state-space models of a reduced fixed-order, in particular, with only 6 states. Figure 2 shows the input-output data of the simulated single generator: a small positive step is induced into the reference voltage (V_{ref}), expressed in p.u., and the corresponding damping response in the active power (P) is registered. Note that default values in the PSS were used so that no specific tuning was adopted to obtain optimal damping, since outside of the present scopes. Note also that these data represent a zero-gain system as the output returns to the original stationary value after the transient effect of the input change, which acts as an external disturbance to be rejected by the PSS. In Figure 2 the output of each identified model is also reported; as a result, all models fit well with the original output and the corresponding NMSE are around 10^{-3} .

As a further confirmation of the validity of the identified models, a good matching of the dominant eigenvalues in the continuous-time domain is obtained. Figure 3 shows that the couple of complex conjugate eigenvalues of the original linearized system, equal to $-1.044 \pm 11.109j$, is well overlapped by the dominant eigenvalues of the four identified models. In particular, $-1.021 \pm 11.224j$ for the N4SID,

Fig. 3. Eigenvalues plots for the single generator: original linearized system and fixed-order linear models.

Fig. 4. Responses of the rotor speed for the single generator: original nonlinear system vs. fixed-order linear models.

$-1.020 \pm 11.224j$ for the MOESP, $-1.021 \pm 11.223j$ for the CVA, and $-0.970 \pm 11.227j$ for the PARSIM-K model.

In addition, the effect of the same step variation of the reference voltage is analyzed on the other system output, that is, the rotor speed (ω_r). Figure 4 shows the response of the original nonlinear system and of the four identified linear models with a reduced order, set to 10 states. The output of each model fits well with the original response since all the NMSE are once again around 10^{-3} .

2) *Model selected with threshold approach in SVD*: As a second scenario, the order of the investigated state-space models is selected on the basis of the dominant singular values in the core SVD of the subspace methods. In particular, all singular values σ_i such that $\frac{\sigma_i}{\sigma_{max}} < T_\sigma$ are discarded, where σ_{max} is the largest one, and T_σ is a calibrated threshold value. Different thresholds were used for different methods to obtain consistent models. As shown in Figure 5, almost all methods, apart from N4SID which exhibits a clear offset, guarantee good models: their output well reproduces the original signal, and the corresponding NMSE is around 10^{-4} . The adopted thresholds are different and the selected orders are pretty similar: with $T_\sigma = 10^{-5}$, $n = 5$ is obtained for N4SID; with 10^{-3} , 6 for MOESP; with 0.8, 14 for CVA; and with 10^{-3} , 4 for PARSIM-K. In terms of eigenvalues matching, the dominant complex conjugate couple of the original linearized system is pretty overlapped by the couples $-1.043 \pm 11.216j$, $-1.021 \pm 11.224j$, $-0.972 \pm 11.226j$, $-0.869 \pm 11.321j$ of CVA, MOESP, N4SID, and PARSIM-K, respectively.

3) *Models selected with IC*: As a third scenario, the three different Information Criteria (IC) available in SIPPY (Akaike, corrected Akaike, and Bayesian) are used as a method for the order selection of the various models. In particular, the

Fig. 5. Time responses for the single generator: original nonlinear system vs. linear models selected with the threshold approach.

Fig. 6. Time responses for the single generator: original nonlinear system vs. linear models selected with AIC.

optimal reduced number of states n is searched in the interval $(5, 20)$. For the sake of brevity, only the results obtained with the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) [21] are here illustrated. The obtained model orders are $n = 9, 11, 10, 13$ for N4SID, MOESP, CVA, and PARSIM-K methods, respectively. As shown in Figure 6, all the tested methods are now able to guarantee a reliable model since their output fits well with the actual signal and the corresponding NMSE is around 10^{-6} . Nevertheless, the optimal model for the various methods is typically of a larger order than what was obtained by the two previous approaches. In terms of eigenvalues matching, as an example, the dominant complex couple of the original linearized system $(-1.044 \pm 11.109j)$ is overlapped by the couple $-1.042 \pm 11.218j$ of the PARSIM-K model.

4) *Input-output models*: In addition, two input-output models are identified for the single generator. An ARX model is obtained with the standard linear least-squares (LLS), and an ARMAX is derived with the iterative LLS scheme implemented in SIPPY. The AIC is used also in this case as a method for the selection of the various model orders; in particular, by searching $n_a, n_b, n_c \in (5, 15)$, and the time-delay $\theta \in (0, 5)$. Best orders are $n_a = 12$ and $n_b = 13$ for the ARX; $n_a = 12$ and $n_b = 13, n_c = 10$ for the ARMAX; $\theta = 0$ for both models. As shown in Figure 7, the actual output is well-fitted by the responses of two models and the corresponding values of NMSE are less than 10^{-7} . Note that input-output models represent a fair alternative to state space formulation for this SISO case as the corresponding formulations are still compact.

B. The two-generator system

In this section, a forward step in terms of complexity is made since a power system comprised of two synchronous generators is analyzed, as shown in Figure 8. Data of one input (the reactive power, in MVAR) and one output (the frequency

Fig. 7. Time responses for the single generator: original nonlinear system vs. input-output linear models.

Fig. 8. Simplified scheme of the two-generator system.

deviation from the nominal value of 50 Hz) are available for the generator n.1; corresponding time trends are reported in Figure 9. Note that this system was simulated with a rigorous software different from *PowerFactory*, so the eigenvalues of the corresponding linearized model were not available. As for the previous case study, the same four sub-space methods were used and all five approaches for the model order selection were tested. For the sake of brevity, only results for the fixed-order approach are here reported. In particular, the corresponding outputs of the 20-state models are shown in Figure 9. Good matching in the time trend of the outputs is obtained for all methods and the corresponding NMSEs are around 10^{-4} .

In addition, as shown by the Bode plots of Figure 10, the identified low-order models can give a good idea of the frequency response of the original nonlinear system which was experimentally evaluated for discrete values. The gain plots lay in the actual span of the system magnitude and the phase plots tend to replicate the overall shape of the true response.

C. The “New England” power system

The last case study considered is the *IEEE 39 Bus System*, a well-known benchmark example in the field of electrical

Fig. 9. Time responses for the two-generator system: original nonlinear system vs. fixed-order linear models.

Fig. 10. Bode plots of the two-generator system: original nonlinear system vs. identified fixed-order linear models.

Fig. 11. Single-line diagram of the New England system.

power engineering. This is a simplified model of the high voltage transmission system of the New England area, in the northeast region of the USA, comprised of 10 generators and 39 buses. Figure 11 shows the single-line diagram of this large power grid as simulated in *PowerFactory*. The considered data are the reference voltage as input and the active power as output, both of generator Gen6: a step test is introduced and the corresponding response is registered. Note that the analyzed subsystem is still a SISO system, but is not isolated; data are generated in closed-loop mode as the considered generator operates within a large-scale power system. Gen6 is indeed subjected to different sources of perturbations from the other grid elements; the other generators and the corresponding controllers are all active, thus producing a very interactive scenario that makes model identification a real challenge. As previously, four different subspace methods (N4SID, MOESP,

Fig. 12. Time responses for the New England system: original nonlinear system vs. fixed-order model with PARSIM-K method.

Fig. 13. Eigenvalues maps of New England system: original linearized system vs. PARSIM-K model.

CVA, PARSIM-K) were investigated and five different approaches for the model order selection were tested.

1) *Fixed-order models*: As a first scenario, state-space models of a reduced fixed-order, that is, with only 10 states, are analyzed. In this case, only the output of the PARSIM-K model is able to fit well with the actual output since its NMSE is around 10^{-9} (see Figure 12). On the opposite, the three traditional subspace methods fail to identify a good model with such a low order; the highly closed-loop data prove to be a limitation for such methods. Note that their output is not reported in Figure 12 for the sake of clarity.

The eigenvalues of the linearized subsystem are available - 156 stable eigenvalues are indeed present - and they can be used for further evaluation of the low-order linear model identified with the PARSIM-K method. As shown in Figure 13, a good matching in the continuous-time domain is obtained: the two couples of identified dominant eigenvalues result located in a sort of centroid of the two clusters of the original eigenvalues. In particular, the average coordinates for the outer cluster (OC) of the true eigenvalues is $-0.742 \pm 8.969j$ and the corresponding identified eigenvalue lies in $-0.718 \pm 9.071j$. The average coordinates of the inner cluster (IC) are $-0.408 \pm 6.947j$ and the corresponding identified eigenvalue lies in $-1.304 \pm 6.919j$. The identified model of reduced order proves to make a good synthesis of the original eigenvalues and then well represents their oscillating behavior.

Fig. 14. Time responses for the New England system: original nonlinear system vs. PARSIM-K model selected with AIC.

Fig. 15. Time responses for the New England system: original nonlinear system vs. input-output linear models.

2) *Models selected with AIC:* As a second scenario, the three information criteria of SIPPY are used as a method for the order selection of the various models; in particular, the optimal reduced number of states is searched in the interval (5, 20). For the sake of brevity, only the results obtained with the AIC are reported. As shown in Figure 14, the PARSIM-K method guarantees a reliable reduced order model (with 6 states): its output fits well with the actual signal and the NMSE is around 10^{-11} . On the opposite, the three traditional subspace methods still fail to produce a good model; note that their output is not reported in the same Figure.

3) *Input-output models:* Finally, two input-output models are identified: an ARX and an ARMAX model. The AIC is once again used as a method for the selection of the various model orders; in particular, by searching $n_a, n_b, n_c \in (5, 12)$, and the time-delay $\theta \in (0, 5)$. As result, best orders are $n_a = 9$, $n_b = 8$ and $\theta = 3$ for the ARX; $n_a = 9$ and $n_b = 10$, $n_c = 6$ and $\theta = 2$ for the ARMAX. As shown in Figure 15, the actual output is well fitted by the response of two models and the corresponding NMSE are around 10^{-11} . Note that input-output models represent a good alternative to state space formulation as the corresponding formulation is still compact being the original subsystem a SISO system.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, practical linear data-driven models are identified for different power systems. Input-output data are generated within a rigorous simulation software and corresponding models are identified and evaluated by using an open-source toolbox developed in Python. Four different sub-space methods are tested (N4SID, MOESP, CVA, and PARSIM-K), and the five different approaches available for the selection of model order are investigated: fixed-order models, threshold definition on singular values, and three information criteria. Since the PARSIM-K method is consistent with data collected

in closed mode, it proves to give the best performance for all the considered case studies: a single synchronous generator, a two-generator system, and even a large-scale power grid. Such reduced-order linear models will be then utilized for tuning different grid controllers, such as Power System Stabilizers. As further future work, reduced-order linear will be identified and compared with suitable data-driven nonlinear models on noisy simulated tests.

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